

Prevalent Misconception: “Anti-Zionism is Antisemitism”¹

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On November 28, 2023, the US House passed a motion stating, “anti-Zionism is antisemitism” (US Government 2023). On November 24, 2023, *the National Post*, a conservative Canadian daily, featured an article headlining: “Don’t Be Fooled – ‘Anti-Zionism’ is just antisemitism, rebranded” (Shalev 2023).

It is not. Equating anti-Zionism with antisemitism is not about challenging antisemitism at all, but part of a drive to silence growing solidarity with Palestinians in the midst of Israel’s genocidal war on Gaza, marking a rhetorical escalation of anti-Palestinian racism (Majid 2022; Abu-Laban and Bakan 2021). Antisemitism is a serious threat, and opposing it without compromise is critical. But it cannot be challenged effectively if its meaning is trivialized or distorted.

Antisemitism has multiple meanings that are often problematically conflated. At its core, the term refers to anti-Jewish racism, which is how I discuss it in this contribution. Another problematic use of the term—forwarded in the examples listed in the International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance (IHRA) working definition of antisemitism—falsely equates criticism of Israel with antisemitism (Gould

2020). The IHRA working definition, for example, claims it is “antisemitic” to ascribe the State of Israel as a “racist endeavor”.

Anti-Zionism, however, is not in any way the same as antisemitism. In fact, Zionism, anti-Zionism and non-Zionism have been discussed in the Jewish community for decades. There are certainly some antisemitic currents, including white nationalism, which use the term “Zionism” as a place saver for Jews, as an object of hate. Indeed, white nationalist currents appropriate many terms and manipulate them to their own aims. But it is not rising white nationalism that has provoked US Republicans and conservative Canadian pundits to express concern about anti-Zionism.

Zionism has taken multiple forms historically, some interpreting Biblical verses to signify a spiritual home for Jews. The dominant form of Zionism today is political Zionism, or what I have termed “really existing Zionism” (Bakan 2014). Zionism is the founding and ongoing ideology of all of the main political parties in the State of Israel. Its premise is that Jews can only live in peace, free of antisemitism, away from non-Jews, in an ethnically defined nation-state.

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Zionism in any form, however, is not the same as Jewish identity, culture, theology, or religion. Indeed, prior to the Holocaust, Zionism was a minority view in the international Jewish community. Jews challenged antisemitism as oppressed peoples have continuously challenged oppression—linking arms in common cause with others to fight for fundamental social change and eliminate oppressive hierarchies. But liberal democratic states offered no safe haven for Jews. The US and Canada blatantly refused Jewish refugees fleeing Nazi Germany. Many Jews looked to socialism—and yet even socialist states failed Jews, adapting, or continuing earlier patterns, of violent anti-Jewish racism.

In 1948 when the state of Israel was established the Jewish population had been decimated. Those surviving WWII were desperate to find a way to imagine a life of peace and safety. In that moment of extreme despair, Zionism came to fill the vacuum. This was a state founded as a colonizing project. Some participated knowingly, others did not, but the outcome was the same. Israel originated as an ethnically defined “Jewish” state, not a state of all its citizens regardless of race or religion. And this apartheid orientation has been reaffirmed repeatedly, including in Israel’s 2018 Basic Law (Government of Israel, Knesset 2018).

The land of historic Palestine comprised a productive, diverse society including a majority of Indigenous Muslim and Christian Palestinians, as well as Mizrahi and some Ashkenazi Jews. The *Nakba*, Arabic for catastrophe, marks the moment of occupation, ethnic cleansing and displacement in 1948. This was not only an historic event, but continued in 1967 and beyond, tragically reaching the present day genocide against the people of Gaza.

Political Science can and should be the disciplinary space that can unpack misguided political rhetoric. It can teach us how to understand Zionism as a political ideology, an “ism”, comparable to other “ism’s”, such as liberalism, anarchism or socialism. If we fail to take up this responsibility, misusages and distortions of terms like “antisemitism” and “Zionism” become hegemonic, with, as we see today, dangerous and tragic political consequences. ♦

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